

Rethinking urban water management through Drivers-Pressures-States-Impacts-Responses framework application in Chennai, India

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1 **Abstract**

2 Cities suffering water scarcity are projected to increase in the following decades. However,
3 the application of standardized indicator frameworks for assessing urban water resource
4 management problems is on an early stage. India is expected to have the highest urban
5 population facing water scarcity in the world by 2050. In this study, the authors assess how
6 the Drivers-Pressures-States-Impacts-Responses framework, a causal framework adopted by
7 the European Environment Agency, can contribute to evaluate water management challenges
8 in cities and apply it to Chennai, India’s fourth-largest urban agglomeration.

9 The framework proved to be a helpful tool for the evaluation of water management challenges
10 in cities by disentangling relationships between environmental indicators and structuring
11 disperse data that allows a better understanding for policy makers. The main drivers identified
12 in Chennai were population growth and economic development which generated impacts such
13 as loss of aquatic ecosystems, low water table, low water quality and reduction of biodiversity
14 and human health. As a response, better urban planning, projects for new water infrastructure,
15 and water bodies restoration have been implemented. Nevertheless, Chennai keeps facing
16 difficulties to achieve a proper water management. The severe hit of COVID-19 pandemic on
17 the Indian economy and its future management will be key for achievements related to water
18 management.

19

20 **Keywords**

21 Water Resources Management, Land-use change, water scarcity, Environmental causal
22 framework, Urban resilience, South India.

23

24

25 **1 Introduction**

26 Cities around the globe are suffering from water scarcity. In 2009, at the end of the “Millennium
27 Drought”, water storage volumes feeding Melbourne fell to a historic low of 25.6% of capacity
28 (Low et al. 2015; van Leeuwen 2017). In 2013 and 2014, Sao Paulo became dependent on
29 reservoirs with available water percentages in the single digits (Millington 2018). In 2018, Cape
30 Town faced a Day Zero in which pipes went dry and people needed to collect drinking water
31 from distribution points (Zetland 2021).

32 Urban water demand will increase by 80% by 2050, while rapid population growth and
33 urbanization of cities put significant pressure on water resources (Newton 2016) and climate
34 change is altering the timing and distribution of water (Flörke et al. 2018). In this context, the
35 number of large cities facing water scarcity was projected to increase from 193 (37%) to 292
36 (56%) and global urban population facing water scarcity was projected to double from 933
37 million (33%) in 2016 to 1.693–2.373 billion (35–51%) in 2050 (He et al. 2021). Consequently,
38 water insecurity will be one of the most severe crisis the world will face during the next several
39 decades (UNESCO and UN-Water 2020). Cities are also facing a problem of water quality
40 with impacts on health and ecosystems (Chaturvedi 2012). In 2020, at least 2 billion people
41 used a drinking water source contaminated with faeces (WHO World Health Organization
42 2020) and 3.6 billion lacked safely managed sanitation (World Bank 2020).

43 India had the highest number of urban inhabitants facing water scarcity worldwide in 2016
44 (222 million people). This is expected to increase to 550 million in 2050, i.e. 26.7% of the
45 world’s urban population facing water scarcity (He et al. 2021). City development and poor
46 institutional control (Chaturvedi 2012; Hossain et al. 2013) have resulted in the pollution of the
47 majority of surface water bodies with untreated sewage (Chaturvedi 2012) and promoted over-
48 extraction of ground water (Wada et al. 2012). Chennai, India’s fourth-largest urban
49 agglomeration, exhibits a complex setup around water resources management that generates
50 social, political and environmental tensions, including water-poor areas where human
51 development is limited (Allen et al. 2006). In 2019, the city hit Day Zero when its four major
52 reservoirs dried up and four million people were relying solely on water tankers (Jayaraman,
53 2019; “Water crisis in Chennai”, 2019).

54 Traditionally, cities relied on large-scale infrastructure for water management, often with
55 systems operating independently of each other (Brown et al. 2009; Marlow et al. 2013).
56 Addressing water management in cities with complex scenarios like Chennai requires an
57 integrated approach, such as the Integrated Urban Water Management (IUWM) process. This
58 approach encompasses water supply, sanitation, stormwater, and wastewater management
59 integrating them with land use planning and economic development (Bahri 2012). The concept
60 of IUWM emerged in the 1980s, highlighting the interconnections between actors, surface
61 water, groundwater, and issues of water quantity and quality and has evolved over the years
62 (Benson et al. 2015; Hoekstra et al. 2018; Manny 2022). In the 1990s, Sustainable Urban
63 Water Management (SUWM) became prominent, driven by growing concerns for ecological
64 health and sustainable development, integrating environmental variables more

65 comprehensively into the discussion (Hoekstra et al. 2018; Pluchinotta et al. 2021). In the late
66 2000s, Adaptive Water Management emerged in response to the need for climate change
67 adaptation (Kirono et al. 2014; Hoekstra et al. 2018). Recently, concepts such as Water Risk,
68 Water Resilience, the Water-Food-Energy Nexus, Total Water Cycle Management (Maurya
69 and Singh 2022), and Water Sensitive Urban Design (van der Meulen et al. 2023) have
70 become influential (Hoekstra et al. 2018). In parallel and since around 2000, water security
71 has also emerged as a central concept, broadly encompassing integrated, sustainable, and
72 adaptive aspects (Hoekstra et al. 2018). The relevance of water security is underscored by its
73 recognition and definitions from the Global Water Partnership (GWP 2000), the World Water
74 Council (WWC 2000), and the United Nations (UN-Water 2013). Over time, the term has
75 evolved to include various attributes, such as affordability, human well-being, water-related
76 disasters, hazard, risk, political stability, and resilience (Romero-Lankao and Gnatz 2016;
77 Chapagain et al. 2022).

78 Although IUWM is a crucial process to prevent water crises regardless of water scarcity (Di
79 Baldassarre et al. 2018) and has the highest potential to reduce pressures on water resources
80 (Koop and van Leeuwen 2015a), there is no internationally standardized indicator framework
81 for it (Koop and van Leeuwen 2015a). This situation compromises the achievement of the
82 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) numbers 6 Clean Water and
83 Sanitation and 11 Sustainable Cities and Communities (United Nations 2015; He et al. 2021).

84 Several models and frameworks are used for analyzing water management, environmental
85 issues and socio-ecological systems: causal-chain frameworks, such as the Pressure-State-
86 Response (PSR), Pressure-State-Impact-Response (PSIR), and the Drivers-Pressures-
87 States-Impacts-Responses (DPSIR), sustainability assessment frameworks, including the
88 Social-Ecological Systems Framework (SESF) and the Ecosystem Services Framework, and
89 integrated water management frameworks, like the City Blueprint and the Asian Water
90 Development Outlook (AWDO) frameworks.

91 The PSR framework emphasizes the relationship between environmental pressures, the
92 current state of the environment, and societal responses (Maurya and Singh 2022), while the
93 PSIR framework incorporates an "Impact" stage (Van Ginkel et al. 2018). The DPSIR, a causal
94 framework for describing the interactions between society and the environment, provides an
95 organized structure to assessing the causes, consequences, and responses to changes in
96 ecosystems (Gabrielsen and Bosch 2003; European Environment Agency 2020). The SESF
97 is used to diagnose the sustainability of social-ecological systems (Ostrom 2009), while the
98 Ecosystem Services Framework categorizes the benefits humans obtain from ecosystems,
99 with an emphasis on natural resource management (Matzdorf & Meyer, 2014). The City
100 Blueprint framework (van Leeuwen et al. 2012; Koop and van Leeuwen 2015b) uses 24
101 indicators across eight categories, including water security, water quality, sanitation,
102 biodiversity, and governance. It measures integrated water resources management
103 performance implemented by local water authorities (Hoekstra et al. 2018) and includes an
104 additional framework for describing significant trends and pressures that may impact water
105 management (Koop and van Leeuwen 2015b). The AWDO framework (Asian Development

106 Bank 2020) assesses water security through five key dimensions: households, economies,
107 cities, the environment, and resilient communities.

108 The DPSIR framework is particularly suitable for urban water management due to its holistic
109 and integrated approach. Simplified frameworks like PSR and PSIR are straightforward, easy
110 to use, and effectively link pressures to state changes and policy responses (Hazzbavi et al.
111 2020). This clarity makes them useful for decision-makers. However, they often lack the depth
112 required for comprehensive urban water management by oversimplifying interactions
113 (Niemeijer and De Groot 2008; Levrel et al. 2009). Compared to SESF and the Ecosystem
114 Services Framework, DPSIR not only addresses sustainability and ecosystem services but
115 also analyzes the system with a holistic approach, which is key for complex scenarios like
116 water management in Chennai. The City Blueprint framework provides a detailed structure but
117 is complex, requiring a dual framework that focuses on water resources management
118 performance as well as trends and pressures. This complexity, along with the need for
119 extensive and specific data, can impede its application, especially in developing countries
120 (Hoekstra et al. 2018). The AWDO framework provides a holistic view of water security by
121 addressing interconnected and interdependent dimensions. However, it is primarily designed
122 for national assessments, includes only five urban-specific indicators, and uses averaged data
123 for all urban areas across a country, which limits its usefulness for IUWM (Jensen and Wu
124 2018).

125 Adopted by the European Environment Agency, the DPSIR framework provides an organized
126 structure to assess the causes, consequences, and responses regarding water management
127 (European Environment Agency 2020), that facilitates communication with stakeholders
128 (Tscherning et al., 2012). Additionally, it has been widely applied to assess the environmental
129 state of cities (Kohsaka 2010), rural communities (Gari et al. 2018a) and river basins (Kong et
130 al. 2016; Pagan et al. 2020a), and has demonstrated its utility to describe cause effect
131 relationships in cases with limited data availability (Gari et al. 2018b), and to develop causal
132 chains (Pagan et al. 2020b).

133 Hence, this study aims to address the following research questions: (i) How can the DPSIR
134 framework contribute to evaluate water management challenges in cities with wicked water
135 problems? (ii) What are common limitations for effective water management in cities located
136 in developing countries and facing resource scarcity? These questions will be addressed
137 through the application of the DPSIR framework to the city of Chennai, India.

138

139 **2 Materials and methods**

140 **2.1 Study area**

141 Chennai, known as Madras until 1996, is the capital of the Indian state of Tamil Nadu. It is
142 located on the southeastern coast of India (13°05'N and 80°18'E), on the Bay of Bengal (Figure
143 1). Nowadays, the Chennai city limits coincide with the Chennai district (Government of Tamil
144 Nadu 2020). According to the 2011 Indian census, the Chennai district had 7,088,000
145 inhabitants in an area of 426 km² (Directorate of Census Operations Tamil Nadu 2011).
146 Chennai city is governed by the Greater Chennai Corporation (Chennai District 2020).

147 The Chennai city district together with parts of Tiruvallur, Kanchipuram and Chengalpattu
148 districts constitute the Chennai Metropolitan Area (CMA) with an extension of 1189 km²
149 (CMDA 2020a) and 8.70 million inhabitants according to the 2011 Indian census (Directorate
150 of Census Operations Tamil Nadu 2011). The Chennai Metropolitan Development Authority is
151 in charge of urban planning in this area.

152
153 Figure 1. Chennai location and water bodies. Source: Authors. Note: India on the globe
154 image, Wikimedia Commons, 2014 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0>). CC
155 BY-SA 3.0

156

157 Chennai has a tropical wet and dry climate (Köppen: Aw) with a relative constant temperature
158 (Rajanikanth and Rajini Kanth 2020). In the period 1971-2000, highest and lowest average
159 monthly temperatures showed annual variations ranging from 28.9 to 37.1°C and from 21.2 to
160 28.0°C and the average monthly rainfall ranged from 2.2 to 407.4 mm (Selvaraj et al. 2016).
161 The hottest part of the year is late May and early June and the coolest is January (Prakash
162 and Punyaseshudu 2015). The average annual precipitation is around 1,400 mm (Rajanikanth
163 and Rajini Kanth 2020). The lowest precipitations occurred in February, during the pre-
164 monsoon season, and the highest from mid–October to mid–December in the northeast
165 monsoon (NE) season (Selvaraj et al. 2016). Regarding climate change, mean temperatures
166 have risen (maximum, 1.6°C; annual, 1.3°C; minimum, 1.0°C) from 1951 to 2010 (Jeganathan
167 and Andimuthu 2013) while rainfall tendency is unclear (Ramachandran and Anushiya 2015;
168 Rangarajan et al. 2018). Concerning floods, Oldenborgh et al. (2016) found no signal for a
169 positive trend in extreme one-day precipitation at the southeastern coast of India over 1900-
170 2014.

171 Chennai is situated on a flat area known as the Eastern Coastal Plains with an average
172 elevation of 6.7 m.a.s.l. and a highest point of 60 m.a.s.l. (Pulikesi et al. 2006). The rivers of
173 Chennai flow from west to east, draining into the Bay of Bengal, and divide the city into north–
174 south sections. Two major rivers are the Cooum River, located in the center of the city, and
175 the Adyar River to the south. A third river, the Kortalaiyar, flows through the northern fringes
176 of the city before draining into the sea, at Ennore. The three rivers are connected by the
177 Buckingham Canal, a fresh water artificial waterway parallel to the Coromandel Coast.
178 Additionally, there are four reservoirs called Poondi, Cholavaram, Puzhal, and
179 Chembarambakkam (Mariappan 2014) and many artificial lakes, locally called tanks that
180 traditionally stored water during the monsoon season that was used for irrigation during the
181 dry season (Devi et al. 2020).

182 The Chennai ecosystem has been dominated by Palmyra and Phoenix palms interspersed
183 with thickets with a mixture of grasses and short herbs in the intervening spaces; allowing free
184 surface water flows and preventing flooding. Trees were sparse and local (Ranjit-Daniels et
185 al. 2020). Pallikaranai Marsh stand out with multiple species of plants, fish, birds, butterflies,
186 and reptiles (Surya 2016) although it has been heavily urbanized within the last 30 years
187 (Coelho 2018).

188

189 **2.2 Application of the DPSIR framework**

190 In this work, we applied the DPSIR framework (Gabrielsen and Bosch 2003; Kristensen 2004;
191 European Environment Agency 2020) and, consequently, defined its components (drivers,
192 pressures, states, impacts, and responses) and its causal chain in relation to water
193 management in the city of Chennai, India. The components of the DPSIR framework and their
194 linkages are depicted in Figure 2 while their definitions can be found in the literature (Smeets
195 and Weterings 1999; Gabrielsen and Bosch 2003; Kristensen 2004; Semeoshenkova et al.
196 2017).

197

198 Figure 2. The components of the DPSIR framework and their connections.

199 The application of the DPSIR framework and the definition of its components involved an
200 extensive literature research in Scopus, Web of Sciences core collection and Google Scholar
201 (Patrício et al. 2016). Also, data reports and other documents provided by public
202 administrations. Thus, the websites of the Chennai Metropolitan Water Supply and Sewerage
203 Board (CMWSSB, also known as Metrowater), Chennai Metropolitan Development Authority
204 (CMDA), Tamil Nadu Water Supply and Drainage (TWAD) Board, Tamil Nadu Pollution
205 Control Board, Central Pollution Control Board, Central Ground Water Board (CGWB) were
206 consulted, as well as the second edition of the master plan of Chennai and renowned
207 newspapers.

208 **3 Results**

209 **3.1 Overview**

210

211 Figure 3 presents the components and causal chain of DPSIR analysis of water management
 212 in Chennai. Also, a table shows the indicators used in this study in the supplementary material
 213 (Table S1).

214

215 Figure 3. Components and causal chain of DPSIR analysis of the water management in
 216 Chennai, India.

217 **3.2 Drivers**

218 **3.2.1 Population growth**

219 Chennai is today a cosmopolitan megacity due to a transformation that started in the last
 220 century and continues in the present. The 20th century brought to Chennai an accelerated

221 population growth rate over a decadal 10% (Figure 4). During the period 2001-2011, the
 222 population growth rate equaled 7.8% due to the almost complete urbanization within the city
 223 limits of that time (174 km²), an average annual growth of 0.75%. Later in 2011, the area of
 224 the city was expanded to 426 km² and its population reached 7,088,000 (Directorate of Census
 225 Operations Tamil Nadu 2011). Considering the new limits, the growth rate in the period 2001-
 226 2011 was above 10%. Since then, the Chennai city limits remain untouched and coincide with
 227 the Chennai district, one of the 38 districts of the State of Tamil Nadu.

228 In parallel to the population, the spatial area of Chennai has expanded from 68 km² to 426
 229 km² since 1901 (Krishnamurthy and Desouza 2015) and the population density has increased
 230 from 1,041 (1981) to 2,109 (2011) persons per km² (Aithal and Ramachandra 2016).

231 The Chennai Metropolitan Area is composed by the Chennai District and parts of Tiruvallur,
 232 Kanchipuram and Chengalpattu districts, the latter carved out of Kanchipuram district in
 233 November 2019 (CMDA 2020a). It has an area of 1,189 km² and 8.70 million inhabitants
 234 according to the 2011 Indian census, the fourth most populated metropolitan agglomeration
 235 in India (Directorate of Census Operations Tamil Nadu 2011). Additionally, its population has
 236 been estimated to be 10.2 million in 2016 (30th-largest in the world) and to reach 13.9 million
 237 in 2030 (United Nations 2016).

238
 239 Figure 4. Population and area of Chennai City (1871-2011) and Chennai Metropolitan Area
 240 (2011-2016). Sources: 1871-1891, Secretary of State for India (1908); 1901-2001, CMDA
 241 (2008); 2011, Directorate of Census Operations Tamil Nadu (2011); 2016, United Nations
 242 (2016). Populations of 2011 from bottom to top correspond to i) the area before the expansion
 243 of the Chennai City District in 2011, ii) the area after the expansion and iii) the metropolitan
 244 area.

245 The constant immigration plays a key role for the population growth of Chennai, with a migrant
 246 population of 918,000 (23.9% over the total) in 1991, and 937,000 (21.57%) in 2001. In the

247 latter, divided into 74.5% from other parts of Tamil Nadu, 23.8% from other parts of India and
 248 1.7% from foreign countries (CMDA 2008). Since 2000, the population from foreign countries
 249 has increased from 35,000 in 2009 to 82,790 in 2011 (Krishnamurthy and Desouza 2015).
 250 Traditionally, the high fertility rate also explained the population growth. However, today in
 251 Tamil Nadu it is among the lowest of the country and it is similar to developed countries
 252 decreasing from 2.5 in 1993 to 1.7 in 2016 (International Institute for Population Sciences
 253 2017; NITI Aayog 2020). This rapid population growth increases the demand for water and
 254 the scarcity and shortages likelihood.

255 3.2.2 Economic development

256 During the British rule of India, Chennai was the capital of Madras Presidency and therefore
 257 the economic center of South India (Haufe 2017). Today, Chennai is one of the most
 258 economically developed and industrialized cities in India, and the largest industrial center in
 259 South India (Bloodgood 2007; Krishnamurthy and Desouza 2015).

260 Several factors have contributed to its explosive economic development. At a national scale,
 261 after the 1947-1991 protectionist period, the economy of India was liberalized and received
 262 massive foreign investments. Since the start of the 21st century, annual average gross
 263 domestic product (GDP) growth has been around 6% to 7% (Kanungo et al. 2018), and from
 264 2014 to 2018, India was the world's fastest growing major economy with an average of 7.4%,
 265 surpassing China (International Monetary Fund 2019). At a state level, Tamil Nadu is the
 266 second largest state in India by GDP and the per capita net state domestic product in
 267 percentage at constant prices of Tamil Nadu (Figure 5) has increased at an average 6.59%
 268 between financial years 98-99 and 18-19 (Reserve Bank of India 2020a).

269
 270 Figure 5. Per capita net state domestic product (NSDP) growth in percentage (rupees) at
 271 constant prices in Tamil Nadu (1998-1999 to 2019-2020). Source: Reserve Bank of India
 272 (2020). Average exchange rate (2021) is 73.9339 INR for 1 USD.

273 At a city level, Chennai received large-scale investments from multinational companies and a

274 tremendous industrialization took place, especially in the automobile, health, IT and banking
275 sectors (Krishnamurthy and Desouza 2015). With an estimated GDP (PPP) of \$78.6 billion in
276 2018, Chennai metropolitan area is the fifth largest city by GDP in India (Haritas 2017). Other
277 important industries include petrochemicals, textiles, apparels and the ports of Chennai and
278 Ennore. The main industrial developments of Chennai took place along three main corridors:
279 the Old Mahabalipuram Road alongside the coast, as IT corridor; the Grand Southern Trunk
280 (GST) Road, towards southwest, as the logistics and industries corridor; and the Chennai–
281 Bengaluru Highway as an automotive and electronic hardware corridor (Haufe 2017). This
282 economic development increases the per capita consumption of water due to new industries
283 and the higher purchasing power of the population (Bao and Chen 2015).

284 **3.3 Pressures**

285 **3.3.1 Land use change**

286 Chennai experienced significant changes in land use because of intense urbanization due to
287 rural to urban migration, the natural increase of population, reclassification of rural settlements
288 into urban, and changes in boundaries of existing urban settlements (Adelina 2015). Urban
289 areas expanded by 173.8% (211.2 km² to 578.4 km²) in the period 1988-2017, i.e. an average
290 annual growth of 1.92%, while rural areas and water bodies shrank as depicted in Figure 6
291 (Mathan and Krishnaveni 2020).

292 Figure 6. Land use change in Chennai Metropolitan Area from 1988 to 2017. Derived from
293 LANDSAT data (Mathan and Krishnaveni 2020).

294 **3.3.2 Groundwater over-extraction**

295 The growing water demand by the increasing industries and population has led to an
296 uncontrolled extraction of groundwater within the city and its peri-urban areas estimated on
297 average in 200 million liters per day (Venkatachalam 2015) despite the Chennai Metropolitan
298 Area Groundwater Act from 1987 prohibition to extract groundwater in 302 villages. This
299 regulation is frequently violated (Butterworth et al. 2007). Many peri-urban farmers have
300 shifted from agriculture to water production (Roumeau et al. 2015) and sell groundwater
301 directly to Metrowater (Ruet et al. 2007) and private tankers (Butterworth et al. 2007). In the
302 city, around 6530 deep bore-wells have been dug (Venkatachalam 2015). The general status
303 of aquifers is monitored by the public authorities (Roumeau et al. 2015).

304 **3.3.3 Liquid and solid waste mismanagement**

305 According to Metrowater (CMWSSB 2020a), Chennai generates 550 million liters per day
306 (MLD) that are treated in 12 sewage treatment plants with a total capacity of 727 MLD. Arappor
307 lyakkam (2017) agrees 550 MLD are treated, but also that around 1500 to 2000 MLD of
308 sewage are generated in the city. Hence, nearly 1073 MLD of sewage would be directly
309 discharged into water bodies and only 33.90% would be treated. Several areas lack access to
310 an efficient sewage system, therefore wastewater is disposed in septic tanks (Thirumurthy

311 2017).

312 Chennai currently exhibits the highest per capita solid waste generation rate in India: 0.65
313 kg/person/day. Municipal Solid Waste generation has increased from 600 to 5400 metric tons
314 per day (MTD) within 20 years with residential (68%) as main origin (Greater Chennai
315 Corporation 2020). Collected waste is disposed with limited processing at two non-technically
316 managed open dumpsites (Greater Chennai Corporation 2020): Kodungaiyur (1.089 km²) and
317 Perungudi (0.809 km²). An important amount of waste remains unattended at collection
318 centers, roadsides, drains and riverbanks (Esakku et al. 2007; Mahajan 2016).

319 **3.4 States**

320 **3.4.1 Urbanization status**

321 Urban areas expanded by 173.8% (211.2 km² to 578.4 km²) in the period 1988-2017 (Mathan
322 and Krishnaveni 2020) and reached 48.7% of the Chennai Metropolitan Area surface (1189
323 km²). Chennai's urban core is intensely developed and is surrounded by rural or peri-urban
324 areas that lack basic amenities. Slums that lack access to water, sanitation and electricity are
325 home to 1.3 million people (CMDA 2006; Saharan et al. 2018) which was estimated to be
326 18.9% of the urban population in 2001 (CMDA 2008) and 28% in 2011 (Directorate of Census
327 Operations Tamil Nadu 2011).

328 **3.4.2 Water availability**

329 Chennai has been historically in water deficit because of the lack of perennial rivers due to the
330 monsoon climate. The city has the lowest per capita water availability of all the metropolitan
331 cities in India (CMDA 2006; Packialakshmi et al. 2011). The water supply is around 90 liters
332 per capita a day and is reduced during the dry period (Feb-Mar). Water demand for Chennai
333 urban area in 2014 was 1173 MLD, while the supply was only 831 MLD (Government of Tamil
334 Nadu 2014).

335 The core of the Chennai Metropolitan Area benefits of a better water supply (Government of
336 Tamil Nadu 2014). In other areas, it is only 30 to 40 liters per capita a day, is only available
337 on alternate days or for only 2 to 6 hours per day (CMDA 2006). Around 20% of population in
338 slums lack of piped water and rely on public fountains and mini tanks (CMDA 2006).

339 Drought events are common in Chennai. Between 2003-2004, the entire piped water system
340 was inoperative. The packaged water market boomed, resulting in a downward spiral of over-
341 extraction of groundwater and unequal water distribution (Roumeau et al. 2015). During the
342 summer of 2019, all the four main reservoirs run dry after two years of scarce rainfall and 200
343 days without rain (Dhillon 2019; Upadhyay 2019). Tap water stopped running and costly
344 private water tankers emerged as alternative water sources (Karthikeyan 2019) making the
345 poor vulnerable (Masih 2019).

346 **3.4.3 Water quality**

347 The numerous sources of pollution, such as sewage discharge, have reduced quality of the

348 water bodies (**Error! Reference source not found.**). All water bodies fail to comply in one or
349 more parameters with the guidelines for propagation of wildlife in surface water provided by
350 Water Quality Standards in India (BIS 1992): pH (6.5-8.5), electrical conductivity (<1000
351 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), dissolved oxygen (≥ 4 mg/L) and BOD (≤ 2 mg/L). Precisely, pH is not meet in the
352 tanks, electrical conductivity and dissolved oxygen in Cooum river and Buckingham Canal,
353 BOD in Adyar river and the three water bodies mentioned previously.

354 Table 1.Values of environmental quality parameters in water bodies of Chennai, India. Results are in surface water (SW), ground water (GW),
 355 sediment (SD) and mussel *Perna viridis* (PV^a: gills; PV^b: hepatopancreas). In the major and trace elements section of the table, results in surface
 356 water and ground water are in mg/L and results in sediments and in *Perna viridis* are in mg/kg. Other abbreviations: Pr: Pre-monsoon. Mo:
 357 Monsoon. Po: Post-monsoon. Dr: dry season. Wt. wet season. BDL: below detection limit.

		In situ parameters														
Water body		pH	EC (μ S/cm)	TDS (mg/L)	DO (mg/L)	Turbidity (NTU)						Reference				
Cooum river	SW - Pr	7.3-7.9	1,696-14,160	1,103-9,820	0-3.8						Dhamodharan et al. (2016)					
	SW - Mo	7.0-7.4	1,510-7,140	920-4,385	0.2-0.4											
	SW - Po	7.3-8.1	2,260-42,400	1,308-25,520	0						Nethaji Mariappan et al. (2017)					
	SW			1,119-20,553	BDL-4.75											
Buckingham Canal	GW	7.5-8.6	1,760-2,540	859-1,611												
	SW	7.24- 8.36	1,546- 2,215	1,422- 4,250	3.5- 5.9	150- 258						Kumar et al. (2018)				
Lakes (tanks): Porur, Perungudi, Velachery, Nandhivaram and Karapakkam	SW	6-8.7											Raji and Abraham (2018)			
Ground water City area	GW	6.0-8.2	580-7,250	374-4,669						Krishna Kumar et al. (2015)						
Ennore creek	SW	6.2-8.1						4.5-6.1						Vasanthi et al. (2017)		
Coast of Chennai	SW - Dr	7.17-8.60						0.00-12.37						Mishra et al. (2015)		
	SW - Wt	7.30-8.70						0-9.98								
		Chemical and biological parameters														
Water body		COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	NH ₃ (mg/L)	NO ₂ ⁻ (mg/L)	NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	TN (mg/L)	PO ₄ ³⁻ (mg/L)	TP (mg/L)	SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	Tot Alk (mg/L)	Chlorides (mg/L)	Reference			
Adyar river	SW		20-78											Kumar et al. (2019)		
	SW - Pr	113-376	35-128	11-18.5	0-0.1	0-2.2			280-4,360	194-440	308-4,829					
Cooum river	SW - Mo	102-236	35-85	9-19	BDL	BDL			140-815	176-340	140-1,529			Dhamodharan et al. (2016)		
	SW - Po	124-396	36-128	11-20	0-0.29	0-2.9			780-6,660	288-549	410-10,147					
	SW	195-1,204	16-375											Nethaji Mariappan et al. (2017)		
	GW								0-4	117-672	165-354	284-347				
Buckingham Canal	SW	640-1,572	146- 511											Kumar et al. (2018)		
Lakes (tanks): Porur, Perungudi, Velachery, Nandhivaram and Karapakkam	SW	13-102	9-34						0.4- 2.4	0.02-0.162						Raji and Abraham (2018)
Ground water City area	GW						0.1-3.9						Krishna Kumar et al. (2015)			
Coast of Chennai	SW - Dr	0.32-148	0-3.15	0-2.37	0-7.62			0-14.02						Mishra et al. (2015)		
	SW - Wt	0.01-168	0.002-2.88	0-0.749	0-4.19			0-20.02								
		Major and trace elements														
Water body		Ca (mg/L)	Mg (mg/L)	Na (mg/L)	K (mg/L)	Zn (mg/L)	Cu (mg/L)	Pb (mg/L)	Cd (mg/L)	Hg (mg/kg)	Fe (mg/L)	Cr (mg/L)	Ni (mg/L)	Reference		
Cooum river	SW - Pr	40-244	24-255	296-4,803	21.3-136								Dhamodharan et al. (2016)			
	SW - Mo	36-144	20-140	208-1,402	10-75											
	SW - Po	208-593	15-43	405-9,250	27-227											
	SW						0.34-2.41	0.11-0.86	BDL-0.09						Nethaji Mariappan et al.	

	GW	40-68	63-107	110-357	3-9							(2017)	
Pallikaranai marshland	SW					0.002–0.14	0-0.02	0.03–1.13	0-0.019	0-1.52	0.10–1.52	0-0.60	Karpagavalli et al. (2012)
	SD					149.4	102	36.6	1.6	0.58	30,201	382	Jayaprakash et al. (2010)
Ground water City area	GW	26-130	1.2-141.6	71-1,200	3-36								Krishna Kumar et al. (2015)
Ennore creek	PV ^a					4.658	3.289	0.761	0.416	8.957			Vasanthi et al. (2017)
	PV ^b					3.378	3.098	0.892	0.315	7.987			

358

359 **3.4.4 Biodiversity status**

360 Encroachment and pollution of natural and artificial water bodies has affected Chennai's
361 aquatic biodiversity. Amali et al. (2019) found that the wetlands located within the coastal
362 districts of Tiruvallur, Chennai and Kancheepuram were only 15.8% of the total area in 2016.
363 In the Pallikaranai marshland species diversity has been reduced due to wetland occupation
364 and wastewater and solid waste pollution. According to Azeez et al. (2007) and Vencatesan
365 (2007), 114 plant and 223 animal species can be found in the wetland, including endangered
366 species. Plants include two endemics to Peninsular India (*Cynodon barberi* and *Iseilema*
367 *enthephroides*), and exotic plants like water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) and water lettuce
368 (*Pistia stratiotes*). 115 bird, 46 fish, 21 reptile, 10 amphibian, 10 mammal, 9 mollusk, 5
369 crustacean and 7 butterfly species have been reported. Raj et al. (2010) reported 101 species
370 of resident and migratory birds. Knight and Devi (2010) found 75 fish species on the freshwater
371 habitats around Chennai.

372 **3.5 Impacts**

373 **3.5.1 Loss of aquatic ecosystems**

374 Urbanization involved occupation, mismanagement and drainage of wetlands and the
375 abandonment of water tanks (Amirtham et al. 2009; Meenatchi Sundaram 2011; Murawski
376 2015). Therefore, water bodies shrank by 30.6%, i.e. an average annual reduction of 1.25%
377 (Mathan and Krishnaveni 2020).

378 The Pallikaranai marshland drained about 250 km² and occupied an area of 56 km² over
379 today's residential localities such as Velachery, Thoraipakkam, Perungudi and Pallikaranai
380 until 1980 (Vencatesan 2007; Sree Sharmila and Swathika 2016). Construction in this area
381 reduced its extension to only 6 km² (Steinbruch and Hörmann 2015; Sree Sharmila and
382 Swathika 2016). In 2005, 0.57 km² were used as a dumpsite and 1.37 km² were impacted by
383 garbage and sewage (Vencatesan 2007). In 2007, 3.17 km² were declared as a Reserve
384 Forest (Vencatesan 2007). Nowadays, there are two garbage-dumping yards in its outskirts.
385 Into the bargain, untreated or partially treated sewage enters the wetland due to direct
386 discharge or the Perungudi sewage treatment plant (The Hindu 2019).

387 Shifting drinking water supply from surface water to ground water sources in the past resulted
388 in the degradation and abandonment of water tanks (Ariza et al. 2007; Palanisami et al. 2008;
389 Adelina 2015). The Tamil Nadu administration tried to change this situation with the Protection
390 of Tanks and an Eviction of Encroachment Act, in October 2007. However, this law has not
391 been fully implemented (Lavanya 2013). Approximately 15% of the water storage capacity of
392 the tanks in Adyar basin was lost due to heavy siltation (Massuel et al. 2014).

393 **3.5.2 Low water table**

394 Groundwater over-extraction and reduced groundwater recharge due to dense urbanization
395 and increase of paved areas have caused declining groundwater levels (Srinivasan et al.

396 2013). Subsequently, aquifers are salinized due to seawater intrusion (Butterworth et al. 2007;
397 Brunner et al. 2014; John 2015).

398 According to the Central Groundwater Board, 80% of Chennai's groundwater has been
399 depleted (Balan et al. 2012) and all of the 20 groundwater assessment units in Chennai are
400 over-exploited. In May 2019 (pre-monsoon), 64% of 11 monitored wells presented a water
401 level of 5 to 10 m and 36% of 2 to 5 m (Central Ground Water Board 2020). Any further
402 exploitation could lead to severe salt water intrusion (Balan et al. 2012). In peri-urban areas,
403 groundwater over-extraction has caused a decline of the groundwater table: the pre-monsoon
404 and post-monsoon groundwater level fluctuation varied from 2–6 m to 0–5 m, respectively,
405 during 1971–2007 (Packialakshmi et al. 2011). An evaluation of the total change in
406 groundwater storage across the state of Tamil Nadu from 2002 to 2012 concluded that
407 groundwater depletion rate is 8% higher than the annual recharge rate (Chinnasamy and
408 Agoramoorthy 2015).

409 **3.5.3 Low water quality**

410 The estimated 1073 MLD of sewage directly discharged into water bodies, together with
411 industrial waste water produced a poor quality status of the aquatic ecosystems of Chennai
412 (Amirthalingam 2003).

413 The Adyar river suffers from agricultural pollution upstream Nandambakkam, where it starts
414 to receive untreated sewage (Venugopal et al. 2009; Lakshmi and Deepa 2011). This river is
415 not perennial and only carries enough water during the rainy season. The rest of the year is
416 almost stagnant due to the lack of water and the formation of sand bars near the mouth
417 (Lakshmi 2011), transporting undiluted effluents from sewage treatment plants (CMDA 2008).
418 The situation is similar in the Cooum river (Dhamodharan et al. 2019). Beyond Vanagram up
419 to its mouth, the river is highly polluted due to its perennial state, siltation, sand bar formation
420 and almost stagnant state (Mukhopadhyay et al. 2020), and the discharges of untreated
421 sewage and industrial waste water (Nethaji Mariappan et al. 2017). Also in the Buckingham
422 Canal, that receives sewage and industrial effluents during its course through the city and the
423 silting up of the canal has left the water stagnant (Jayaprakash et al. 2012). Encroachment in
424 some sections of the central area has shrunk its width from 100 m to 10 m (2019b).

425 The lakes and the Pallikaranai marshland have suffered from encroachments, dumping,
426 burning of wastes and sewage and industrial waste water discharge (Shahina et al. 2020).
427 The Pallikaranai marshland is additionally polluted by the non-isolated Perungudi dumpsite
428 (Padmavathi 2007). High concentrations of Cd, Hg, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, and Zn were found in its
429 sediments (Jayaprakash et al. 2010). Sea water has intruded up to 16.5 km inland in Minjur -
430 Panjetty area due to over exploitation of groundwater (Government of India 2017).

431 Seawater is polluted nearby the river mouths of the Adyar and the Cooum rivers by high
432 concentrations of nutrients, low dissolved oxygen, high biochemical oxygen demand (BOD)
433 and chemical oxygen demand (COD), high total suspended matter, high trace elements
434 (Shanmugam et al. 2007; Mishra et al. 2015), high level of coliforms, *Vibrio* and *Pseudomonas*,
435 (Santhiya et al. 2011), and presence of antibiotic resistant pathogens (Vignesh et al. 2012)

436 and microplastics (Kumar et al. 2016).

437 **3.5.4 Reduction of biodiversity and human health**

438 Amali et al. (2019) found that the wetlands located within the coastal districts of Tiruvallur,
439 Chennai and Kancheepuram have decreased to 31.6%, from 23.1% in 1988 to 15.8% in 2016,
440 i.e. an average annual reduction of 1.35%.

441 The degradation of aquatic ecosystems in Chennai has impacted its biodiversity. Invasive
442 species, like the ornamental fish suckermouth, have been introduced and affected local
443 species population (Oppili 2017). Water hyacinth colonized and significantly affected the
444 biodiversity in Pallikaranai Marshland (Surya 2016). The construction of roads fragmented the
445 marshland and limited the movement of animals (Azeez et al. 2007), with a reduction of
446 resident birds in general (Vencatesan 2007) and the Black-winged Stilt in particular from 836
447 individuals in 2000 (Subramanian 2000) to 150 in 2010 (Raj et al. 2010).

448 For Buckingham Canal, the changes in the water quality reduced the primary productivity,
449 affecting the entire aquatic ecosystem (Kumar et al. 2018). In Ennore estuary, 15 species were
450 found dead in large numbers in August 2014 (Sachithanandam et al. 2017). High
451 concentrations of Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in *Mugil cephalus* fish and ultrastructural
452 alterations on the green mussel *Perna viridis* have been found (Arockia Vasanthi et al. 2013;
453 Vasanthi et al. 2017). At the discharge site of the power plant located in Ennore, the population
454 density of phytoplankton and zooplankton is reduced by 64% and 93%, respectively (Prince
455 Prakash Jebakumar et al. 2018).

456 The pollution of water resources has also adversely affected Chennai's inhabitants health.
457 The stagnant water in Buckingham canal creates an attractive habitat for malaria-spreading
458 mosquitoes (Jayaprakash et al. 2012). Water-borne diseases like Diarrhea and Typhoid are
459 common (Sethuram 2014). Drinking water in some areas was highly contaminated with
460 coliforms, *Cryptosporidium* and *Isospora* (Anbazhagi et al. 2007; Lavanya 2013; Chopra and
461 Dworkin 2013), including sachet water but not bottled water (Venkatesan et al. 2014).

462 **3.6 Responses**

463 **3.6.1 Urban planning**

464 Chennai has had two master plans for urban planning. The First Master Plan for Chennai
465 Metropolitan Area was approved in 1976 and the Second is in force since September 2008
466 (CMDA 2020b). Nevertheless, the urban form of the Chennai Metropolitan Area has been
467 dictated by developments along the major roads and rail links radiating from the center of
468 Chennai into the peri-urban regions (CMDA 2008). The second Plan included chapters for
469 infrastructure for water supply and sanitation, with a recommendation to allocate water to
470 areas within the city and outside, and for environment, with a recommendation to reduce
471 pollution levels to acceptable standards in the waterways of Chennai. Recently, the
472 elaboration of a third master plan with long-term vision document produced through a
473 participatory approach has been announced, being planned to be implemented from 2026 and

474 to last for two decades (Shivakumar 2020).

475 **3.6.2 Water infrastructure**

476 Chennai has developed a big water infrastructure consisting on dams and interbasin transfers,
477 groundwater pumping, rainwater harvesting, desalination plants and water tankers.

478 Over 90% of the water supply of Chennai is covered by water stemming from reservoirs
479 (Brunner et al. 2014; Sakthivel et al. 2015). Surface water is provided mostly through two
480 systems of interconnected reservoirs. The oldest system has three reservoirs at Poondi (91.5
481 hm³) and Cholavaram (25 hm³), that discharge into Puzhal (93.5 hm³), also called Red Hills.
482 This water is treated at Puzhal (300 million liters per day, MLD), Kilpauk (270 MLD) and
483 Surapet (14 MLD) (CMDA 2006; CMWSSB 2020b). The newest system has
484 Chembarambakkam reservoir (103,2 hm³) and Chembarambakkam Water Treatment Plant
485 (530 MLD) (CMDA 2006; CMWSSB 2020b).

486 When water is scarce, around 500 MLD water from the Srisailem reservoir in the Krishna
487 River, can be diverted towards Poondi Lake through a series of 400 km-long inter-linked
488 canals called the Telugu Ganga project (CMDA 2006). Also, Veeranam lake and Vadakuthu
489 Water Treatment Plant (180 MLD) are added to the system. In total, the capacity of the cited
490 water treatment plants is 1,294 MLD (CMWSSB 2020c).

491 Groundwater's contribution has significantly diminished due to overexploitation
492 (Packialakshimibb et al. 2011; Sakthivel et al. 2015) from a maximum of 25% to around 6%
493 during the 2000's (Brunner et al. 2014). Because of low water level in the inner-city,
494 Metrowater started to hire private peri-urban agricultural wells in 2000 that yielded 77 MLD in
495 2005 compared to only 5.99 MLD of previous wells (CMDA 2006). Currently, Metrowater
496 continues extracting in peri-urban areas: Minjur, Panjetty, Tamaraipakkam Poondi and
497 Kannigaiper (CMWSSB 2020d). In fact, most of the agricultural wells in the villages in the
498 Chennai Metropolitan Area feed the inner city water market through water tankers
499 (Packialakshimibb et al. 2011) depriving peri-urban farmers of irrigation water (Butterworth et
500 al. 2007). In the southern peri-urban interface, 17.1 MLD are extracted by private water tankers
501 and 19.2 MLD by packaged water industries (Packialakshimibb et al. 2011). Also many
502 households in Chennai have in-house wells (Ruet et al. 2007).

503 To improve this situation, installation of Rain Water Harvesting (RWH) structures became
504 mandatory for new buildings in 2002 (CMWSSB 2020d). Since then, 38,218 structures have
505 been constructed (CMWSSB 2020d) with high acceptance by the public (Vivek 2016) but
506 maintenance issues were reported (Ministry of Water Resources and Government of India
507 2011).

508 Since 2010, a 100 MLD seawater desalination plant is operating at Minjur, north of the city,
509 and a similar 100 MLD plant at Nemmeli, south of the city, since 2013 (CMWSSB 2020e). A
510 third 150 MLD plant is expected to be completed by April 2023 (Lakshmi 2022) and a fourth
511 400 MLD at Perur by 2024 (Lakshmi 2019).

512 Tanker-based water supply is estimated to be 21% of the total water supplied in Chennai

513 (Maheshwari et al. 2020) i.e. around 125 MLD (Venkatachalam 2015), that would be delivered
514 by up to 20,000 daily tanker loads of water (The Hindu 2018). About 80% of households in the
515 Chennai Metropolitan Area consume packaged drinking water instead of piped water (The
516 Hindu 2018). About 15-20 MLD of packaged drinking water are sold in the city daily (Srinivasan
517 2008).

518 **3.6.3 Sewage treatment**

519 The total installed wastewater treatment capacity in Chennai reaches 727 MLD in 12 sewage
520 treatment plants, however, it is estimated that nearly 1073 MLD of sewage are directly
521 discharged into water bodies (Arappor lyakkam 2017). The 12 treatment plants are divided in
522 zones from I to V and their treatment capacity ranges from 12 to 120 MLD. In Nesapakkam,
523 Koyambedu and Kodungaiyur, plants use activated sludge process and in Villivakkam an
524 aerated lagoon (CMDA 2020b). In 2005 and 2006, the Chennai City River Conservation
525 Project (CCRCP) invested Rs. 7201.5 million to increase the sewage treatment capacity,
526 prevent overflow of sewage into the city waterways and renovate part of the system (CMDA
527 2006).

528 **3.6.4 Restoration of water bodies**

529 There are several projects to restore Chennai's water bodies. The Chennai Rivers Restoration
530 Trust, founded in 2006 by Government of Tamil Nadu as Adyar Poonga Trust, have three
531 projects: the Eco-Restoration of Adyar Creek (58 acres), the Eco-Restoration of the Adyar
532 Creek and Estuary (300 acres) and the Integrated Cooum River Eco-Restoration Plan
533 (Chennai Rivers Restoration Trust 2020).

534 The non-governmental organizations (NGOs) Care Earth Trust and The Nature Conservancy,
535 among others, have developed wetland restoration projects introducing a sustainability and
536 community participation focus. Care Earth Trust has successfully completed the restoration of
537 the Narayanapuram Lake, the Perungalathur Periya Eri, the Puduthangal Lake, Thazhambur
538 Eri, the Sembakkam Lake, the Puducheri Keni kulam and the Odai keni kulam (Care Earth
539 Trust 2020).

540 In the Pallikaranai marshland, 317 ha of its southernmost portion were declared as a bird
541 sanctuary on April 2007 (Vencatesan 2007; Steinbruch and Hörmann 2015) and its declaration
542 as Ramsar site is in progress (Shekhar 2020).

543 **3.6.5 Water governance**

544 The Chennai Metropolitan Water Supply and Sewerage Act, 1978, amended in 1997, also
545 known as Tamil Nadu Act 28 of 1978 founded Metrowater and gave it the mission to provide
546 the Chennai Metropolitan Area an adequate supply of good quality water and a safe disposal
547 of waste water at a reasonable price (CMWSSB 2020f). Metrowater subsidizes its residential
548 customers by overpricing its industries (Gopakumar 2009). According to their data, 830 million
549 liters per day (MLD) of drinking water are produced in Chennai, whereas the treatment
550 capacity reaches 1,494 MLD. The expansion to cover the whole Chennai Metropolitan Area is

551 in progress (CMWSSB 2020c). A few years later, the Chennai Metropolitan Area Ground
552 Water (Regulation) Act, 1987 came into force to preserve ground water and gave Metrowater
553 the power to authorize permits to sink wells and licenses for extraction and the obligation of
554 keeping well registers and the use of groundwater for agricultural purposes (The Chennai
555 metropolitan area groundwater (regulation) act 1987 1987). Furthermore, The Tamil Nadu
556 Pollution Control Board is responsible for setting, monitoring and enforcement of
557 environmental regulations and standards (Roumeau et al. 2015).

558 Current approaches to water governance struggle to meet Chennai's demands for water.
559 Legislation exists but for political, institutional and social reasons it is not always enforced
560 (Janakarajan and Lakshmi 2005).

561 The insufficient supply of water by public entities has made private owned tankers and the
562 packaged water vendors critical actors in water governance (Roumeau et al. 2015). Many
563 farmers have left their agricultural activities to sell groundwater directly to private tankers
564 following a greater revenue (Packialakshmi et al. 2011; Roumeau et al. 2015). Other
565 stakeholders are water suppliers in the private sector, farmers, and the civil society (Roumeau
566 et al. 2015) as well as multiple NGOs dealing with water and environmental issues, like
567 Environmentalist Foundation of India or the Care Earth Trust.

568 **4 Discussion**

569 Different studies have assessed the DPSIR framework in terms of its application for
570 sustainable development studies (Carr et al. 2009), determination of causal relationships
571 (Niemeijer and De Groot 2008) and its feasibility for supporting decision making (Tscherning
572 et al. 2012). These authors enunciate that the DPSIR presents drawbacks regarding to its
573 hierarchical structure, the establishment of unidirectional relationships and, in some studies,
574 the lack of integration of decision makers into the participative process. Nevertheless, they
575 also stress the DPSIR's potential to emphasize causality between environmental indicators
576 and to structure disperse data to provide meaningful explanations of complex environmental
577 issues to policy makers (Niemeijer and De Groot 2008; Tscherning et al. 2012) that facilitates
578 communication and comparison (Patrício et al. 2016). Since the development of the DPSIR,
579 25 derivatives in more than 152 studies have been proposed in the literature (Taft and Evers
580 2016; Patrício et al. 2016). However, none has been adopted by the scientific community as
581 a replacement for the DPSIR nor by international institutions as the original DPSIR framework
582 was by the European Union and European Environment Agency (European Commission 1999).

583 Through the application of the DPSIR in Chennai, the authors agree on its advantages and its
584 potential to be connected with the SDGs 6 and 11. The application of the DPSIR involves
585 indicators regarding water resources and pollution, waste, land use change, and loss of
586 biodiversity among others (Smeets and Weterings 1999; Kristensen 2003; European
587 Environment Agency 2005, 2014) that are also included in the SDGs 6 and 11, like the
588 indicators 6.3.1 Proportion of domestic and industrial wastewater flows safely treated, 6.3.2
589 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality or 6.6.1 Change in the extent of
590 water-related ecosystems over time and 11.3.1 Ratio of land consumption rate to population

591 growth rate (United Nations 2022a, b).

592 The application of the DPSIR framework also found limitations on water management. First,
593 water management requires to be faced from several perspectives and considering a large
594 number of variables. Today, decision-makers and stakeholder work in many cases
595 independently with contradictory interests. Therefore, a deeper integration of the public
596 administration bodies involved in water management and a better cooperation of different
597 stakeholders is necessary. Secondly, poor law enforcement hinders efficient water
598 management. For example, groundwater over-extraction in periurban areas. Thirdly, data
599 scarcity or difficult access impedes to develop new efficient policies adapted to the city needs.

600 In the Indian context, the implementation of effective policies to manage water challenges in
601 cities is limited by inaccessible and unreliable data, limited coordination between stakeholders,
602 non-implementation of policies and projects, environmental legislation violations, unclear or
603 overlapped responsibilities, inadequate maintenance of water infrastructure (Aartsen et al.
604 2018). The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD 2015) provides
605 a framework to understand water governance systems' performance. In addition, the
606 implementation of adaptive management approaches has been stated as a comprehensive
607 solution for improving decision making and managing water resources (Pahl-Wostl 2008;
608 Kattel 2019a). For instance, Kattel, 2019, has proposed six key elements for enhancing water
609 security in river basins i.e. the implementation of early warning systems, water footprints
610 management, groundwater aquifers management, increased water stewardship and
611 governance, enhanced resilience of social and ecological systems of freshwaters and the
612 promotion of the water-energy-food nexus.

613 Chennai and its metropolitan area are expected to keep facing water stress and difficulties to
614 implement the SDGs 6 and 11. The current water supply system has proven to be insufficient
615 even with average weather conditions, with a gap of 342 MLD between estimated demand
616 (1173 MLD) and supply (831 MLD) in 2014 (Government of Tamil Nadu 2014) and with a
617 supply of only around 90 liters per capita a day (CMDA 2006). Chennai needs to urgently find
618 new water sources to meet the always increasing demand.

619 Conventional surface water sources, like new reservoirs, are fed by Northeast Monsoon and
620 would face a similar trend of drought (Chennai Metropolitan Development Authority, 2006).
621 Catchments depending on the Southwest Monsoon are far from Chennai and would require
622 high costs to build and operate long channels and tensions between communities would
623 emerge, like in the Telugu Ganga project. Groundwater is unable to supply sufficient water in
624 a sustainable manner. Recharging the aquifers by water harvesting would contribute to a more
625 stable and reliable water supply. The two new seawater desalination plants (2x500 MLD)
626 planned for 2024 can cater more than 2 million people, although a final affordable water price
627 has to be granted for poorer areas. Otherwise, water bills could remain unpaid as it happens
628 in the rest of the state of Tamil Nadu (Gopakumar 2009). Furthermore, management of brine
629 produced by desalination plants requires to be considered.

630 Chennai's water bodies are being polluted because of the lack of waste water treatment plants.

631 The likely 1073 million liters per day (MLD) gap between treated (550 MLD) and non-treated
632 (1500-2000 MLD) sewage is directly discharged into water bodies (Arappor Iyakkam 2017;
633 CMWSSB 2020a). However, it is insufficient to cover the present and future sewage
634 generation. The authorities need to find funds to build new sewage treatment plants and an
635 efficient waste management system, including the closure of the current two main open
636 dumpsites. The ability of the institutions to implement urban plans that consider sewage
637 treatment and waste management systems will be key for pollution prevention of water bodies
638 at a lower cost. The third master plan of Chennai brings a new and promising focus with a
639 long-term vision document produced through a participatory approach.

640 Biodiversity in the Pallikaranai marshland and other water bodies has been reduced due to
641 increased water pollution and invasive species like the water hyacinth (Oppili 2017). NGOs
642 like Care Earth Trust, The Nature Conservancy and Environmentalist Foundation of India play
643 a major role in the restoration of aquatic ecosystems. Restoration success relies significantly
644 on the interest of the institutions to implement this kind of projects on their own or with the help
645 of NGOs and also in the ability of these NGOs to achieve external funds.

646 Environmental regulations need to meet international standards and to be enforced to ensure
647 the protection of the aquatic ecosystems (Janakarajan and Lakshmi 2005). In May 2020, a
648 new draft of the Environment Impact Assessment Notification 2020, under the Environment
649 (Protection) Act, 1986 came into force. It set aside several essential provisions such as public
650 consultation and introduced ex-post facto clearance for many projects, including some
651 irrigation and hydroelectric projects, all inland waterway projects, and others (Ananthakrishnan
652 2020). This sets a worrying precedent that could affect other environmental regulations.

653 The severe hit of COVID pandemic on Indian economy dropped investment growth in the year
654 2020 to 10% (United Nations 2021) and this will probably delay many of the mentioned
655 projects.

656 **5 Conclusions**

657 This study applied the DPSIR Framework to water management in Chennai, South India. The
658 study provides answers to the research questions raised in the introduction section. First, the
659 DPSIR proved to be a valuable tool to evaluate water challenges in cities by disentangling
660 relationships between environmental indicators and structuring disperse data that allows
661 policy makers for a better understanding. The indicators used for the DPSIR framework can
662 be also easily aligned with the indicators of the Sustainable Development Goals 6 and 11.
663 Second, limited integration of decision-makers and stakeholders, poor law enforcement and
664 scarcity of data limit effective water management in Chennai, which can be applied to other
665 cities with similar scenarios.

666 As a result of the DPSIR analysis, the unplanned population growth fueled by the rapid
667 economic development were identified as the two main drivers. They brought pressures such
668 as rapid land use change, groundwater over-extraction to partially cover the higher water
669 demand, and bigger volumes of solid wastes and untreated sewage that are discharged into
670 water bodies. This situation headed to low values of indicators related to the status of

671 urbanization, water availability, water quality and biodiversity and visible environmental
672 impacts within the city: loss of aquatic ecosystems and encroachment, low water table levels,
673 low water quality, that reduces aquatic biodiversity and human health. Urban planning and the
674 third Chennai master plan was identified as a key response. Stakeholders executed numerous
675 water infrastructure projects that increased drinking water availability with conventional (dams
676 and interbasin transfers, groundwater pumping) and non-conventional (desalination plants,
677 water tankers, rainwater harvesting) techniques. They also built sewage treatment plants,
678 restored ecosystems and improved water governance.

679

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1136 **Supplementary material**

1137 Table S1. Main indicators considered for every component of the Drivers-Pressures-States-
1138 Impacts-Responses analysis of water management in Chennai in this study.

		Indicator	Value	Years	Source
Drivers	Population growth	Average annual population growth (%)	0.75	2001-2011	Directorate of Census Operations Tamil Nadu (2011)
	Economic development	Average annual growth of per capita net state domestic product in rupees at constant prices in Tamil Nadu (%)	6.59	1998-1999 to 2018-2019	Reserve Bank of India (2020)
Pressures	Land use change	Average annual increase of urban area (%)	1.92	1988-2017	Mathan and Krishnaveni (2020)
	Groundwater over-extraction	Average groundwater extracted (million liters per day)	200	2015	Venkatachalam (2015)
	Liquid and solid waste mismanagement	Waste water treated (%)	33.90	2017	Arappor Iyakkam (2017)
States	Urbanization status	Urban area over the total of the Chennai Metropolitan Area (%)	48.7	2017	Mathan and Krishnaveni (2020)
	Water availability	Water supply (liter/inhabitant/day)	90	2014	Government of Tamil Nadu (2014)
	Water quality	Biochemical oxygen demand (mg oxygen/l)	9-375	2015-2019	Kumar et al. (2019); Dhamodharan et al. (2016); Nethaji Mariappan et al. (2017); Kumar et al. (2018); Raji and Abraham (2018); Krishna Kumar et al. (2015)
	Biodiversity status	Wetland area over the total of the Chennai Metropolitan Area (%)	15.80	2016	Amali et al. (2019)
Impacts	Loss of aquatic ecosystems	Average annual reduction in water surface (%)	1.25	1988-2016	Mathan and Krishnaveni (2020)
	Low water table	Water extracted of the aquifer (%)	80	2012	Balan et al. (2012)
	Low water quality	Untreated waste water discharged (million liters per day)	1073	2017	Arappor Iyakkam (2017)
	Reduction of biodiversity and human health	Average annual reduction in wetlands (%)	1.35	1988-2016	Amali et al. (2019)

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